

RESEARCH ARTICLE

POLYMER
ENGINEERING
AND SCIENCE

WILEY

Machine learning for screw design in single-screw extrusion

Nickolas D. Polychronopoulos^{1,2} | Konstantinos Moustris¹ |
Theodoros Karakasidis³ | Janusz Sikora⁴ | Volodymyr Krasinskyi⁵ |
Ioannis E. Sarris¹ | John Vlachopoulos⁶

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of West Attica, Athens, Greece

²Polydynamics, Inc., Dundas, Ontario,
Canada

³Condensed Matter Physics Laboratory,
Department of Physics, University of
Thessaly, Lamia, Greece

⁴Department of Technology and Polymer
Processing, Faculty of Mechanical
Engineering, Lublin University of
Technology, Lublin, Poland

⁵Łukasiewicz Research Network-Institute
for Engineering of Polymer Materials and
Dyes, Toruń, Poland

⁶Department of Chemical Engineering,
McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario,
Canada

Correspondence

Nickolas D. Polychronopoulos,
Department of Mechanical Engineering,
University of West Attica, Athens, Greece.
Email: polyrtheo@polydynamics.com

Funding information

HORIZON EUROPE Marie Skłodowska-
Curie Actions, Grant/Award Number:
101129698-PROMATAI-Horizon-MSCA-
2022-SE-01

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) methods have significantly impacted various areas of technology, particularly in fields where large datasets are available. Screw designs are proprietary, and there is very limited information available in the open literature. In this study, we generated a dataset of 232 designs using computer simulation software for screw extrusion, involving solids transport, melting, and melt pumping. The parameters (features) and the outputs (targets) were introduced into four powerful machine learning (ML) algorithms. The capabilities of the four algorithms were assessed by comparing the predictions of each of the algorithms to the corresponding results of the simulations. Three of the algorithms demonstrated satisfactory performance, with the best-performing one being further tested on an “unseen” dataset, which involved a screw of 75 mm and another of 127 mm in diameter. A machine-learning technique called Permutation Feature Importance (PFI) was used to identify the features (parameters) with the greatest impact on the predictions. It is suggested that the same ML methodologies could be applied to datasets of existing real screw designs.

Highlights

- Dataset obtained from simulation software.
- Four machine learning algorithms were employed.
- Assessment of algorithms based on training and testing data.
- Identification of parameters having greatest impact.
- Satisfactory predictions of mass flow rate, exit temperature, melting length, and more.

KEYWORDS

assessment of predictions, dataset generation, ML algorithms, Permutation Feature Importance, simulation

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Polymer Engineering & Science* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC on behalf of Society of Plastics Engineers.

1 | INTRODUCTION

The screw extruder is the workhorse of the polymer processing industry. The vast majority of the 400 million tons of polymers produced annually go at least once in their lifetime through an extruder. The pelletization process, after the polymerization reactors, is usually carried out with the help of twin-screw extruders. Single-screw extruders are used in the conversion of polymer pellets, powders, and flakes into film and sheet, pipe and tubing, fibers, profiles, cable, wire, and sheet coating and injection molding of numerous plastic products. The heart of the single-screw extruder is an Archimedean screw in a closely fitting cylindrical heated barrel, with just sufficient clearance to allow unimpeded rotation. Solid polymer particles are fed from a hopper; they are compacted as they are transported forward, melted, and pumped through a die for the purpose of shaping into the desired product.

The historical developments of screw design and the operating principles of the single-screw extrusion are described in textbooks by Bernhardt,¹ McKelvey,² Schenkel,³ Tadmor and Klein,⁴ Zhu,⁵ Tadmor and Gogos,⁶ Chung,⁷ Spalding and Campbell,⁸ Rauwendaal,⁹ Agassant et al.,¹⁰ and Vlachopoulos and Polychronopoulos.¹¹ Innovations in screw design have led to significant increases in output rates. Numerous patents have been issued, but the designs can be classified into two groups: conventional single-flight screws and barrier screws. A sketch of a single-flight screw with feed, compression, and metering zones is shown in Figure 1. The ratio of the channel depth in the feed (H_f) to that in the metering section (H_m) is called the compression ratio. There are screw designs having a decompression zone in the form of a secondary metering zone for the avoidance of excessive shear heating at high rotational speeds. Barrier screws include a secondary flight in the compression zone. The barrier screws separate the packed bed of solids from the melt, and they are more efficient in melting than conventional screws. In groove feed extruders, the barrel is grooved near the hopper to a length of up to about 4D. The grooves are either parallel to the axis or helical. In grooved-feed extruders, the screw channels are shallow, and compression is very low (frequently 1.2) while in smooth barrel extruders, it usually ranges from 1.75 to 4. Grooved feed extruders

FIGURE 1 Schematic representation of a single-flight screw.

build very high pressure in the feed zone, which results in high output rates, as the drag flow is aided by pressure. There are modern extruder designs where the barrel is grooved over its entire length, and they can operate at very high rotational speeds with very high outputs.^{12,13}

The innovations, and numerous modifications thereof, were developed in response to the production of new resin grades having special processing requirements. The objective is to maximize the extruder output rate, without any unmelted material emerging from the extruder and to minimize the temperature for the avoidance of degradation. Polymers are nearly always extruded together with additives (stabilizers, colorants, processing aids, flame retardants), fillers (mostly inorganic materials to reduce cost), reinforcements (glass, natural or carbon fibers to increase strength and stiffness), or other polymers (for combination of beneficial properties). Consequently, extruder designs capable of providing good quality mixing are absolutely necessary. Most screws include a mixing device near the end of the metering zone. In North America, in film and sheet production, smooth barrel extruders with barrier screws are used, having a mixer (frequently of Maddock or Egan design¹¹), while in Europe grooved feed extruders are used extensively. Mixers are crucial in grooved extruders due to the high output rates. Conventional, single-flight screws can process a wider range of polymers than barrier-type or other special designs. They are frequently used in injection molding where the diameters are smaller than in extrusion, and melting with help from heat conduction is more significant than in large diameter machines. Conventional screws, usually of small diameters, are used extensively in 3D printing.^{14,15}

Screw extrusion is also used for food,¹⁶ ceramics,¹⁷ cement,¹⁸ pharmaceuticals,¹⁹ and even metals.²⁰ Mathematical modeling of extrusion of plastics and rubber was initiated in the 1950s as discussed in the textbooks cited previously. In fact, the innovations mentioned above were enabled by the understanding provided by the mathematical models. The various modeling methodologies developed for polymers were subsequently extended or modified for other materials. There are enormous mathematical modeling challenges due to the fact that the vast majority of screw extrusion processes involve transport of solid particles, change of phase from solid to melt and melt pumping under non-isothermal non-Newtonian conditions. The implementation of data-driven approaches may enable rational extruder screw design without the need to deal with the intricacies of flow of particulate matter, melting in geometrically complex channels, and non-Newtonian non-isothermal flow.

In the present study, four powerful machine learning (ML) algorithms are employed for a dataset generated from computer simulations of conventional polymer

single-screw extrusion. The rationale is that if ML methodologies could provide reasonable agreement to simulations, they could also be used in the future for harnessing knowledge from existing screw designs.

2 | DATA GENERATION FOR MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning (ML) is usually described as a branch of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on using data and algorithms to identify patterns and make predictions and gradually improve the accuracy of the predictions without human intervention. ML approaches are usually divided into three general categories: (i) supervised learning, (ii) unsupervised learning, and (iii) reinforcement learning. Supervised learning typically involves the process of machine learning to learn a function that maps an input to an output based on data of input–output pairs. The most common tasks in supervised learning are “classification” that separates the data, and “regression” that fits the data.²¹ In unsupervised learning, the algorithm does not have a specific or correct output to guide the learning process. Instead, it tries to find hidden patterns, groupings, or relationships within the data on its own. Reinforcement learning is the task of machine learning in which an agent learns to make decisions by engaging with an environment. The agent performs actions to maximize a reward over time. It learns by experimenting (receiving rewards for good actions and penalties for bad ones) and gradually refines its approach (known as a policy) to achieve the best possible results in the long run. This process is comparable to training a pet (agent), where rewards reinforce good behavior and corrections address mistakes.^{22,23}

The success of ML and AI methodologies in several areas of technology is due to the availability of extremely large quantities of data in digital form, what is frequently referred to as “big data.” For example, machine learning is very successful in computer vision for identifying visual patterns because of the existence and easy availability of millions of images. However, for the design of structures or machines, datasets are difficult or impossible to find. There are some exceptions: the UIUC Airfoil Database²⁴ is a dataset of 1600 real airfoil designs, and recent investigations have added the associated lift and drag values. Wollstadt et al.²⁵ describe a 3-D dataset of more than 10,000 car hood shapes along with the associated mechanical performance data. There is nothing remotely equivalent for extruder screws due to confidentiality and intellectual property issues.

For the present investigation, we decided to follow the methodology described in a publication by Regenwetter et al.²⁶ in an entirely different research area. It was a

supervised learning regression approach for the structural performance prediction of bicycle frames. Regenwetter et al.²⁶ used a dataset of 4500 bicycle frames sourced from designers who used the BikeCAD software.²⁷ Their Finite Element analysis was validated through a mesh convergence study against physical testing of bicycle frames. In the present investigation, we use a proprietary software package called Nextrucad²⁸ for the generation of our dataset.

The methodology used in the development of Nextrucad was originally based on a PhD thesis by Agur,²⁹ also described by Agur and Vlachopoulos,³⁰ subsequently modified with the help of additional insights gained by Castillo³¹ and Castillo et al.,³² and finally converted to a commercially available user-friendly package. For solids transport, the Darnell and Moll³³ model is used, taking into consideration the work of MacGregor et al.³⁴ For melting, the Tadmor model³⁵ as modified by Chung³⁶ is employed. For polymer melt flow, the original 2D finite difference analysis of Agur and Vlachopoulos³⁰ was replaced by a control volume flow analysis along the spiral channels. In addition to conventional screw designs, Nextrucad is capable of simulating barrier screws of Maillefer and parallel type and screws with mixers of Maddock and Egan type. By inputting screw geometry, rheological and thermophysical properties, and operating conditions, Nextrucad predicts pressure profile, solid bed width, and temperature profile along the screw axis, as well as output rate, power, and average residence time. Figure 2 shows a comparison to experimental measurements of pressure and temperature, and the calculated solid bed width for one set of operating conditions in extrusion of HDPE in a 38-mm diameter machine. A summary of predictions and comparisons is shown in Tables 1 and 2 for LDPE.

We carried out 232 simulations of conventional screws with dimensions presented in Table 3. The same table also includes the rheological and thermophysical properties of the polymer, which are typical for polyolefins (e.g., HDPE, LDPE, LLDPE). To reduce the number of parameters, we decided to consider three barrel-heating zones of equal length for all the simulations, with temperatures: 185/195/210°C. The data at the top of Table 3 are the inputs (also called features) that will be fed into each ML algorithm. Guided by the results produced by the Nextrucad software,²⁸ we use the following parameters as outputs (frequently referred to as targets), also to be fed into each ML algorithm: (i) Mass flow rate (kg/h), (ii) Maximum pressure (MPa) along the screw, (iii) Extruder exit temperature (°C), (iv) Melting length (in D), (v) Power (kW), and (vi) Average residence time (s). The value range of each target is presented at the bottom of Table 3. Machine learning based on results

FIGURE 2 Comparison of the experiments by Agur and Vlachopoulos³⁰ (points) to NEXTRUCAD software (continuous lines) for HDPE at $N = 60$ rpm. (A) Axial pressure profile, (B) bulk temperature profile, and (C) relative solid bed width along the screw.

obtained from extrusion simulations was also implemented by Gaspar-Cunha et al.^{37,38} Moreover, Marschik et al.³⁹ and Herzog et al.⁴⁰ used ML algorithms to predict

TABLE 1 NEXTRUCAD comparison to the experiments by Agur and Vlachopoulos,³⁰ for LDPE at different screw speeds.

Screw geometry and process conditions

$D = S = 38$ mm (square pitched screw)
 $L_f = 12D, L_c = 6D, L_m = 6D$
 $e = 6.35$ mm
 $H_f = 6.1$ mm, $H_m = 2.0$ mm
 Barrel temperature profile: 163/179/196/196/196°C
 Die diameter = 7 mm, Die length = 150 mm

LDPE rheological and thermophysical properties

Power-law viscosity model $\eta = m_o e^{-b(T-T_o)} \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$ parameters:
 $n = 0.41, m_o = 6581$ Pa·s^{0.41}, $T_o = 190^\circ\text{C}, b = 0.0165^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
 $\rho_m = 779$ kg/m³, $\rho_s = 919$ kg/m³, $\rho_{\text{bulk}} = 595$ kg/m³,
 $T_m = 110^\circ\text{C}$
 $C_{p,m} = 2595$ J/kg·°C, $C_{p,s} = 2763$ J/kg·°C, $k_m = 0.182$ W/m·K,
 $\Delta H_f = 129,785$ J/kg

Mass flow rate (kg/h) comparison

Screw speed	Experiment	Nextrucad
40	6.879	6.772
60	10.613	10.195
80	14.284	13.591

Bulk temperature in the die (°C) comparison

Screw speed	Experiment	Nextrucad
40	197.59	198.63
60	200.57	199.78
80	201.32	200.46

Maximum pressure (MPa)

Screw speed	Measured ^a	Nextrucad
40	13.78	17.61
60	14.14	21.14
80	18.76	23.83

^aThe location of the pressure probe was not necessarily the location of maximum pressure.

pumping and viscous dissipation in the melt-conveying zone of single-screw extruders.

3 | MACHINE LEARNING

3.1 | Methodology

In the present study, we use supervised learning algorithms, performing regression to the dataset of 232 simulations (20 inputs and 6 outputs in each simulation) obtained from Nextrucad. As explained in section 2, Nextrucad is based on the combination of the analysis of solids transport, melting, and melt pumping using the control volume method. Numerical convergence is fast,

TABLE 2 NEXTRUCAD comparison to the experiments by Castillo et al.,³² for an LDPE grade at different screw speeds.

Screw geometry and process conditions		
Screw diameter = 88.9 mm, Extruder length (L/D) = 30.32		
Feed section (L/D) = 6.0, 1st trans. Section (L/D) = 1.71,		
Melting section (L/D) = 14.0		
2nd trans. Section (L/D) = 1.60, Metering section (L/D) = 7.01		
Start depth of solid channel = 12.7 mm, End depth of solid channel = 3.81 mm		
Start depth of melt channel = 4.06 mm, End depth of melt channel = 11.05 mm		
Primary flight width = 8.89 mm, Primary flight clearance = 0.09 mm		
Barrier flight width = 4.32 mm, Barrier flight clearance = 1.14 mm		
Barrel temperature profile: 193/216/213/207/204/200°C		
Dow 133A 0.3 MI LDPE rheological and thermophysical properties		
Power-law viscosity model $\eta = m_o e^{-b(T-T_o)} \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$ parameters:		
$n = 0.339$, $m_o = 19,169 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^{0.41}$, $T_o = 190^\circ\text{C}$, $b = 0.035^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$		
$\rho_m = 750 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\rho_s = 918 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\rho_{\text{bulk}} = 595 \text{ kg/m}^3$,		
$T_m = 110^\circ\text{C}$		
$C_{p,m} = 2300 \text{ J/kg}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$, $C_{p,s} = 2763 \text{ J/kg}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$, $k_m = 0.24 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$,		
$\Delta H_f = 117,000 \text{ J/kg}$		
Mass flow rate (kg/h) comparison		
Screw speed	Experiment	Simulation
42.6	124	113.68
93.4	239	255.16
Bulk temperature in the die ($^\circ\text{C}$) comparison		
Screw speed	Experiment	Simulation
42.6	224	217.42
93.4	224	225.16
Maximum pressure (MPa)		
Screw speed	Measured ^a	Simulation
42.6	29.13	25.98
93.4	31.98	30.14

^aThe location of the pressure probe was not necessarily the location of maximum pressure.

and a simulation is completed in less than a minute. However, for each simulation, the user must manually input values for the 20 parameters of Table 3. Automated generation of inputs and outputs is not possible. A schematic representation of the methodology is shown in Figure 3.

Traditionally, in ML, particularly for regression, the dataset is split into two datasets of different sizes. The first dataset is the training dataset, which is the main dataset to teach the model. The aim is for the model to learn relationships between the input values (screw

TABLE 3 Inputs and outputs and corresponding values of the dataset.

Inputs (features)		Specified values
D (mm)	Screw diameter	25.4, 90, 150
L/D	Screw length	24, 30, 36
L_f (in D)	Feed section length	7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15
L_c (in D)	Compression section length	3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14
L_m (in D)	Metering section length	7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15
S (in D)	Screw pitch	0.8, 1.0, 1.2
e (mm)	Flight width	2.54, 9.0, 15.0
H_f (mm)	Screw depth at feed	5.5, 13.0, 19.25
H_m (mm)	Screw depth at metering	1.38, 1.57, 1.83, 2.2, 2.56, 3.25, 3.71, 4.33, 4.81, 5.20, 5.50, 6.05, 6.42, 7.70, 8.95
N (rpm)	Rotating speed	30, 50, 60, 80, 90, 100, 120, 140, 150
n	Power-law index	0.3, 0.45, 0.6
m ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}^n$)	Consistency index	5×10^3 , 2×10^4 , 3.5×10^4
b ($^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$)	Temperature sensitivity	0.015, 0.03
ρ_m (kg/m^3)	Melt density	760, 780
$C_{p,m}$ ($\text{J/kg}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$)	Melt specific heat	2300
T_m ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Melting temperature	109, 125, 133
k ($\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$)	Melt thermal conductivity	0.2, 0.25
ΔH_f (kJ/kg)	Heat of fusion	215, 240
ρ_s (kg/m^3)	Solid density	920, 950
$C_{p,s}$ ($\text{J/kg}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$)	Solid specific heat	2300
Outputs (targets)		Value range
Mass flow rate (kg/h)		3.58–1590.82
Max. pressure (MPa)		0.83–139.51
Exit temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)		192.79–330.18
Melting length (in D)		8.04–36
Power (kW)		0.63–387.57
Avg. residence time (s)		46.99–383.54

diameter D , channel depth in the metering section H_m , speed of rotation N , etc.) and the output values (mass flow rate, melting length, power, maximum pressure, etc.) from the data of Table 3. Both the inputs and the outputs are “seen” by the model in the training phase.

Numerical simulations
(Nextrucad software)

FIGURE 3 Schematic representation of the machine learning methodology.

The size of the training dataset that we adopt is 90% of the initial dataset. The rest, 10% of the initial dataset, is referred to as the testing dataset. This split size was selected from previous ML studies.^{41–43} The testing dataset is a separate dataset used to evaluate the performance of a trained machine learning model. In the testing phase, the model only “sees” the inputs (features) when making predictions. The outputs are hidden from the model, and the predicted ones are compared with

the actual ones to evaluate the model's performance. While the training dataset is used during the model-building process, the testing dataset is only used after the model has been trained and fine-tuned. It provides an unbiased assessment of the machine learning algorithm to generalize to the new data.

A common data pre-processing technique is feature (input) scaling. Without scaling, features with larger numerical values may dominate the model's learning

process, causing features with smaller ranges to have a reduced impact.^{44,45} Following Karakasidis et al.⁴⁶ and Benos et al.,⁴⁷ features are scaled using the following equation:

$$Z = \frac{X - X_{\text{mean}}}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where Z denotes the scaled feature, X the unscaled one, X_{mean} the mean value of the feature, and σ the standard deviation.

The following ML algorithms were employed: (i) Decision Trees (DT), (ii) Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), (iii) Support Vector Regressor (SVR), and (iv) Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Below we briefly summarize the architecture of these algorithms.

Decision Trees (DT) is a widely used supervised machine learning algorithm, applicable for both classification and regression tasks. They work by creating a tree-like model where internal nodes represent attribute tests, branches represent outcomes, and leaf nodes represent class labels or prediction values.⁴⁸ DTs are favored for their intuitive and easy-to-visualize structure, and their ability to handle nonlinear interactions. However, they are sensitive to small changes in data, prone to overfitting, and can struggle with modeling smooth functions. To mitigate these issues, techniques like Ensemble Bagged and Boosted Trees are often employed.⁴⁹

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is a powerful machine learning algorithm that excels in tasks like regression and classification. XGBoost is an ensemble learning method. Ensemble learning methods combine multiple individual models to create a more powerful model known as an ensemble model. The XGBoost algorithm combines multiple decision trees to build a more accurate and robust model. XGBoost works by iteratively adding trees, with each new tree focusing on correcting the errors of the previous ones.^{48,50} The algorithm uses gradient descent to optimize the loss function (i.e., mean or absolute errors) during training, enhancing the model's generalization performance and quick convergence. Known for its speed, efficiency, and accuracy, XGBoost is widely used by data scientists and machine learning practitioners. However, its complexity can lead to longer training times and may require careful algorithm tuning.

The Support Vector Regressor (SVR) is a supervised learning algorithm that extends the principles of Support Vector Machines (SVM) to regression tasks.^{51,52} SVM is primarily used for classification problems where the goal is to separate data points into distinct classes. It works by finding the optimal hyperplane that best separates data points of different classes in a high-dimensional space.

SVR aims to find a function that best fits the data within a certain error margin while minimizing the model's complexity.⁵³ Support vectors are the data points that lie outside the error margin and contribute to defining the regression function. Kernel functions can be used to map the data into a higher-dimensional space, allowing for the modeling of nonlinear relationships.⁵⁴ SVR is effective for high-dimensional data and provides good generalization performance. Like XGBoost, SVR can be computationally expensive for large datasets.

Artificial Neural networks (ANNs) are a specific type of ML model. In this case, the model has interconnected nodes aiming to function similarly to those of a human brain. By this way, the model is capable of learning and identifying possible relationships, correlations, and patterns between input and output data.⁵⁵ There are various types of ANNs. In the present work, we have developed a large number of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) predictive models. MLP consists of one Input Layer, one or more Hidden Layers, and one Output Layer.⁵⁶ On each one of these layers there are a number of artificial neurons, which are interconnected. Each input value is then multiplied by a weighting factor. The sum of these multiples is added to the bias term. Finally, a known activation function performs a pre-specified (usually a nonlinear) mathematical operation on the projected inputs. Different activation functions such as sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent are traditionally used for this purpose.^{57–59}

The DT, XGBoost, and SVR algorithm scripts were written in PyCharm Community Edition (free) environment, using *scikit-learn*, a widely used open-source machine learning library for Python.⁶⁰ The script for ANNs was implemented in Matlab 2024a using the *Deep Learning Toolbox*.

3.2 | Algorithm tuning

Algorithm tuning is a necessary step in the process of machine learning. It refers to the process of finding the optimal set of the so-called hyperparameters for a machine learning model. Examples of hyperparameters include the number of branches in a decision tree and the number of hidden layers in a neural network. These hyperparameters are not learned from the data, but they are set prior to training the model.⁶¹

An approach to select the hyperparameters for any ML algorithm is to implement hyperparameter optimization. For the ML algorithms written in Python (DT, XGBoost, SVR), we use the method or technique called Grid Search Cross-Validation (GridSearchCV module in Scikit-Learn⁶⁰). GridSearchCV systematically searches through a predefined set of hyperparameters, called grid,

to find the optimal combination for a given machine learning model. The given values can be discrete or a range. Following the approach by Kavzoglu and Teke,⁶² we carried out a rigorous examination of the literature,^{51,62–69} to identify the most important hyperparameters and value ranges for each ML algorithm. To evaluate the machine learning model performance for each combination of hyperparameters, GridSearchCV implements cross-validation (CV).⁷⁰ Using CV ensures that the results will be more robust and avoid overfitting. CV involves splitting the training dataset into k -folds. In the present study, we set a 5-fold CV as shown in Figure 3, in accordance with other papers.^{71,72} This means that the model is trained on 4-folds and validated on the remaining 1-fold. Afterwards, the average performance score (e.g., root mean squared error, mean absolute error, mean squared error) across these 5-folds is computed for each combination of hyperparameters. Then, GridSearchCV identifies the combination of hyperparameter values that gave the best average performance score. In the present study, we follow Liu et al.⁷³ and select the mean absolute error as the performance score. The optimal hyperparameter value combination is the one that gives the lowest mean absolute error. In the final step, the machine learning regressor is now trained on the complete training set (without any further splits) using the best hyperparameter values. For ANNs, a similar grid search technique was used in Matlab 2024a.

3.3 | Performance evaluation

After the hyperparameter tuning explained in the previous section, the trained machine learning algorithms are tested on the testing dataset. As explained earlier, in the testing phase, the predictive capacity of the ML algorithms is evaluated on new inputs that belong to the testing dataset. In the present work, for the models evaluation, we use two scores. The first one is the coefficient of determination (R^2), which is a measure of how well the predictions approximate the actual data. It ranges from 1, meaning a perfect fit, to negative values, which typically suggests that the model predictions are very inaccurate. The coefficient is determined by

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_t - y_p)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_t - \bar{y}_t)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where n is the total number of samples in the dataset, y_t the true value of the output, y_p the predicted value of the output, and \bar{y}_t the mean value of the true output.

The second metric we use is the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) given by

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left| \frac{y_t - y_p}{y_t} \right| \times 100. \quad (3)$$

It provides a clear and interpretable measure of the magnitude of the prediction accuracy of each ML model.

Finally, we use the ML learning algorithm that achieved the best scores described above (i.e., lowest MAPE and highest R^2 values) to predict the outputs (mass flow rate, maximum pressure, melting length, etc.) of several screw designs with some totally new input values (features) that do not exist in the initial dataset presented in Table 3. For example, the initial dataset includes three different screw diameters: 24.5 mm, 90 mm, and 150 mm, and the ML algorithms are trained and tested on these values. Screw diameters of 75 and 127 mm are totally new feature values that have not been previously “seen” during training and testing.

4 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The figures in this section show scatter plot predictions by the different ML algorithms used. Such scatter plots are customary in the ML community because they provide a visual assessment of how well an ML regression model is performing. For each plot, the horizontal axis corresponds to the actual values, in the present case the results from Nextrucad numerical simulations. The vertical axis holds the predicted values by each ML algorithm. There are two sets of data shown in each scatter plot, one corresponding to training and the second to testing. The diagonal continuous line has a slope of 45°. The training and testing data points must lie as close as possible to the line, which suggests the capacity of the ML algorithm to learn the patterns between the inputs and outputs and, given previously unseen inputs, to predict the corresponding outputs.

Figure 4 shows the comparison of predicted output values from the Decision Trees (DT) algorithm against actual values obtained from the numerical simulation. For the case of mass flow rate, the training data are clustered tightly around the diagonal line, indicating that the model performs well on the data it was trained on. The testing data generally exhibit a high scatter level.

This suggests that the predictive capacity of the DT algorithm to unseen data is not good. Therefore, for this target, DT can learn the features-targets patterns, but it cannot generalize. This is a classical overfitting issue. In ML, overfitting occurs when a model learns the training

FIGURE 4 Scatter plot predictions by Decision Trees (DT). On top of each plot is the name of the output (target).

data too well, capturing not only the underlying patterns but also random fluctuations or noise in the data. In this way, the model becomes too specialized to the training set and fails to make predictions on new data (testing dataset). For the maximum pressure, although some points lie close to the diagonal, there are several data points with a high scatter for both the training and testing datasets, but still following the straight-line trend. This indicates that DT, for this target, learned partially the dataset patterns and its generalization capacity to unseen data is poor. For the extruder exit temperature target, there is an overfitting behavior, similar to the mass flow rate target. For the melting length, the scatter of both datasets is somehow lower than for the maximum pressure target, but still, the DT algorithm struggles to learn and generalize. Similar behaviors are observed for the power and the extruder average residence time. Conclusively, the performance of the DT algorithm on the dataset is generally poor.

Figure 5 displays the comparison of predicted output values against the numerical values for the XGBoost algorithm. The training datapoints of nearly all the targets lie very close (if not exactly) to the diagonal, except perhaps the case of the melting length with some minor scatter. For the testing datapoints, of the mass flow rate,

maximum pressure, and melting length targets, some points are to some extent off the diagonal line, suggesting that for these targets, although XGBoost is trained very well, there is some minor loss in its predictive capacity to unseen data.

Figure 6 illustrates the results for the SVR algorithm. Generally, the training and testing data are on the diagonal line. The mass flow rate, maximum pressure, extruder exit temperature, and power predictions are overall similar to the ones by the XGBoost algorithm. For the melting length target, the training and testing datasets are somehow more clustered along the diagonal line than the corresponding ones by the XGBoost algorithm, which suggests that for this target, SVR performs perhaps better than XGBoost. However, this is not the case for the average residence time, where the XGBoost learning and predicting capacity is clearly better than SVR.

Figure 7 provides the scatter plots obtained by the ANNs. The training and testing data for the mass flow rate, maximum pressure, and extruder exit temperature targets, as in the SVR algorithm, are clustered along the diagonal line, which suggests that ANNs have similar learning and predicting behaviors as the XGBoost and SVR algorithms. For the melting length target, some small scatter is observed around the diagonal line,

FIGURE 5 Scatter plot predictions by XGBoost.

suggesting the performance of the ANNs for this target is less accurate than the SVR but perhaps still close to the XGBoost algorithm. The testing dataset of the extruder power consumption target using ANNs also exhibits some level of scatter, which was not the case for the SVR and XGBoost algorithms. For the case of the extruder residence time target, the training data exhibit more scattering than the SVR algorithm. This means that for this target, SVR learns the underlying pattern better than the ANNs. This is also reflected in the testing dataset, with SVR showing less scatter around the diagonal line than ANNs. It is also evident that, for this target, the XGBoost algorithm has a superior performance.

A comparison of the R^2 and $MAPE$ values of the testing dataset for all the targets for each ML algorithm provides more information on the generalization capacity of the models. These are shown in Table 4. For the mass flow rate target, SVR and ANNs have the same best coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.999$, but SVR has the smallest percentage error, $MAPE = 3.21\%$. For the maximum pressure, extruder exit temperature, melting length, and extruder power consumption, the SVR gives the lowest $MAPE$ scores and the highest R^2 values. For the average residence time target, the XGBoost has the best scores: $MAPE = 2.42\%$ and $R^2 = 0.994$. By comparing the

results of Table 4 altogether, the DT algorithm gives the worst performance for all targets which was expected since in Figure 4 the testing data have a lot of scatter. The performance of the other three ML algorithms is generally comparable, but since the SVR algorithm gives the best scores in five out of the six targets, we proceed with the SVR regressor.

As a final evaluation step, we test the SVR algorithm by inserting several new feature values within the initial dataset range. We selected the parameters that appear to have significant influence on the outputs, namely screw diameter and power-law viscosity. Note that several other feature values are totally new: they do not exist in the initial dataset, and SVR was never trained or tested on these values. We recognize six different cases, presented in Table 5. In Case 1, we select a screw with a new diameter, $D = 75$ mm with $n = 0.52$ and $m = 10,000$ Pa·s^{0.52}. The rest of the features values are taken from the original dataset. Case 2 has the $D = 75$ mm screw diameter, but on top we add the new $L/D = 26$, $S = 1.1$, $e = 7.3$ mm, $H_f = 11.54$ mm, $H_m = 4.21$ mm, and modify $n = 0.42$, $m = 22,500$ Pa·s^{0.42}, and $b = 0.02^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. Case 3 has the new values of Case 2, but we modified $n = 0.32$, $m = 30,000$ Pa·s^{0.32}, and $b = 0.03^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. Case 4 has similar new features to Case 1, with the difference that the screw

FIGURE 6 Scatter plot predictions by Support Vector Regressor (SVR).

has a larger diameter $D = 127$ mm. Case 5 has the $D = 127$ mm screw diameter with new feature values of $L/D = 27$, $S = 1.1$, $e = 13.2$ mm, $H_f = 15.76$ mm, $H_m = 6.45$ mm, and the material rheology is similar to Case 2. Finally, in Case 6, we embed the new features of Case 5, and for the material rheology, we selected the parameters of Case 3. The rest of the features not mentioned above have values from the original dataset. It should be noted that in the Python script for SVR, the above six new screw design and material rheology cases are supplied to the script in the form of a table (e.g., Excel file) and they are evaluated simultaneously.

A comparison of the above six cases with results from the numerical simulations software is shown in Figure 8. For the mass flow rate, it is observed that generally the SVR algorithm produces results very close to the numerical simulations, except for Case 6, where the numerical simulation gives a higher mass flow rate value than SVR. Satisfactory overall agreement is observed for the maximum pressure target with some difference in the values of Cases 1, 3, and 4.

Proceeding to the comparison of the exit temperature target, the results are good for all cases. For the melting length target, the SVR predictions are satisfactory compared to the numerical simulations. For the extruder

power consumption target, the comparison is satisfactory for most of the cases, but not for Cases 1 and 5. Finally, for the average residence time, the comparison between SVR and numerical simulation is not satisfactory for Cases 3 and 6. The failure of SVR to provide satisfactory predictions in some of the cases with totally “unseen” data is an indication that the dataset of 232 screw designs (involving 18 inputs [features] and 6 outputs [targets]) is relatively small. As explained in a previous section of this paper, machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) methodologies are most successful in areas where there is an abundance of data in digital form. Of course, with the available numerical simulations software, the dataset could be significantly augmented. However, the objective of this investigation was not to develop a data-driven replacement for the existing simulation software, but rather to gain insights into the requirements for data-driven approaches in extruder screw design.

We further examine the influence of the features on each one of the six targets for the SVR algorithm. This is carried out with the widely adopted method of Permutation Feature Importance (PFI), originally proposed by Breiman⁷⁴ for Random Forests machine learning. It should be mentioned that PFI is an integral part of the so-called interpretable machine learning. According to

FIGURE 7 Scatter plot predictions by Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs).

TABLE 4 Performance comparison of the selected machine learning algorithms for the testing dataset.

Target	XGBoost		SVR		DT		ANNs	
	MAPE (%)	R^2	MAPE (%)	R^2	MAPE (%)	R^2	MAPE (%)	R^2
Mass flow rate (kg/h)	9.54	0.991	3.21	0.999	25.09	0.841	9.2	0.999
Max. pressure (MPa)	10.22	0.987	7.67	0.992	99.01	0.485	11.4	0.991
Exit temp. (°C)	0.58	0.996	0.28	0.998	1.97	0.933	0.4	0.997
Melting length (in D)	2.23	0.989	1.42	0.994	12.77	0.524	2.0	0.992
Power (kW)	9.22	0.998	8.77	0.999	19.33	0.937	9.5	0.995
Avg. res. time (s)	2.42	0.994	5.97	0.981	13.57	0.891	15.1	0.935

Note: Bold fonts denote the best values.

TABLE 5 Validation cases with totally new feature values (indicated in bold lettering) for predictions using the SVR algorithm.

Case	D	L/D	L_f	L_c	L_m	S	e	H_f	H_m	N	n	m	b	ρ_m	T_m	k	ΔH_f	ρ_s
#1	75	30	12	9	9	1	9	13	3.25	50	0.52	10,000	0.015	780	133	0.25	240	950
#2	75	26	9	8	9	1.1	7.3	11.54	4.21	100	0.42	22,500	0.02	780	133	0.25	240	950
#3	75	26	9	8	9	1.1	7.3	11.54	4.21	150	0.32	30,000	0.03	780	133	0.25	240	950
#4	127	30	12	9	9	1	9	13	3.25	50	0.52	10,000	0.015	780	133	0.25	240	950
#5	127	27	9	9	9	1.1	13.2	15.76	6.45	100	0.42	22,500	0.02	780	133	0.25	240	950
#6	127	27	9	9	9	1.1	13.2	15.76	6.45	150	0.32	30,000	0.03	780	133	0.25	240	950

FIGURE 8 Bar plot comparison of the Support Vector Regression (SVR) algorithm predictions with the ones by Nextrucad numerical simulations, for the totally new feature values of Table 5.

Molnar,⁷⁵ “Interpretability is the degree to which a human can consistently predict the model’s result.” The greater the interpretability of a machine learning model, the easier it is for someone to understand why certain predictions have been made by the model. The core idea in PFI involves measuring the increase in prediction error of the trained model after permuting (shuffling) the values of a feature (while holding the remaining features constant), disrupting in this way its relationship with the outcome.⁷⁵ A feature is considered important, if shuffling its values leads to a significant increase in model error, indicating that the model relied heavily on that feature for accurate predictions.⁶⁸ The “*permutation_importance*” function was obtained from the Scikit-Learn⁷⁰ package and embedded in our Python script. The shuffling process for each feature is repeated 1000 times⁷⁶ and the permutation importance for each feature is the average value corresponding to the increase in the mean absolute error (MAE).⁷⁷

The PFI analysis for SVR is illustrated in Figure 9. For the case of mass flow rate target the most important feature is the screw diameter, followed by another three screw geometrical parameters and screw speed of approximately equal contribution. This result aligns reasonably well to the theoretical result of the drag flow equation reported in several textbooks,^{4–11} where the mass flow rate is proportional to D^2 and depends linearly on H_m , N ,

and e . For the maximum pressure target, PFI ranks the channel depth in the metering section (H_m) as the most importance feature. The polymer rheological parameters m and n have equal importance but to a lesser extent compared to H_m . It can easily be shown, as explained by Vlachopoulos and Polychronopoulos,¹¹ the maximum possible pressure in a single-screw extruder scales with H_m in the following way: $P_{\max} \sim 1/H_m^2$ and depends linearly on D , L , N , and material viscosity, for Newtonian fluids. For the exit temperature target, the most important feature is the screw speed N , followed by the material rheological properties n and m . For the melting length, the screw depth in the metering section H_m has the most dominant impact, followed by screw speed N and the shear-thinning behavior of the polymer (n). Power consumption appears to roughly follow the ranking of the mass flow rate target, with the screw diameter as the most dominant feature. Finally, the average residence time depends mainly on the screw speed. Generally, the screw geometrical characteristics and screw speed have a large impact, followed by the material rheological parameters. The importance of the thermophysical properties of the material is relatively low.

Perhaps by limiting the number of targets to the absolutely necessary, better results could be obtained without increasing the dataset size. The essential targets are the mass flow rate, temperature at the exit, and whether

FIGURE 9 Permutation Feature Importance (PFI) plot for the Support Vector Regression (SVR) algorithm. The vertical axis corresponds to the features. The Permutation Importance value on the horizontal axis is the average increase in the mean absolute error after shuffling each feature 1000 times. Lines next to each bar show the standard deviation.

the polymers are melted upon emerging from the extruder. Also, a machine learning technique known as data augmentation could be investigated.^{78,79} This would produce new, so-called synthetic data, from the existing dataset, without having to run the simulations. Such investigations will be necessary for paving the way for ML and AI tools to be used with real screw designs, keeping in mind that the availability of good data might be limited.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a data-driven approach to single-flighted screw design for polymer extrusion. We developed a dataset of 232 screw designs having different

diameters, lengths, compression ratios, and screw pitch for a rather wide range of rheological parameters and rotational speeds, using a commercially available software package for extrusion simulation. We have presented comparisons of the simulation software predictions to experimental data for a 38 and an 88.9 mm diameter screw, so that the reader will have an appreciation of the capabilities of the software package.

Four powerful machine learning (ML) methodologies were employed: (i) Decision Trees (DT), (ii) Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), (iii) Support Vector Regressor (SVR), and (iv) Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Their performance was assessed by comparing scatter plots (of predicted versus simulated values), mean average percentage error (MAPE), and coefficient of determination (R^2) for mass flow rate, maximum pressure, exit temperature,

melting length, power, and average residence time. XGboost, ANN, and SVR gave good performance for the testing data set, with SVR having a somewhat better overall score. SVR was subsequently used for predicting extruder performance with previously “unseen” six sets of parameters involving two screws (75 and 127 mm) and a rather wide range of power-law viscosity constants. The comparison with simulations was good or satisfactory in most of the cases.

ML models with high predictive power, like SVR and XGBoost used in the present study, once trained, can offer rapid predictions with minimal computational cost. This is particularly advantageous in iterative design, where multiple design variations need to be evaluated quickly. The six different designs presented in Table 5 were carried out in less than 1 s using the trained SVR algorithm. This capability allows for the exploration of a broader design space without the need for extensive simulations. When a satisfactory design is accomplished, an extrusion simulation package may then be used for final tuning that includes determination of the axial pressure and temperature profile and perhaps other flow field details. The feature importance can guide screw design optimization efforts by focusing on the most critical parameters for improvement of the extrusion process, including reduction of energy consumption, avoidance of unmelts, and enhancement of overall product quality. It can also aid in troubleshooting by identifying the features most likely to be causing problems.

Although the machine learning procedures were applied to a dataset derived from an extrusion simulation package, they can also be applied to datasets of actual screw designs. From the six targets involved in the present study, at least three (mass flow rate, exit temperature, and power) are likely to be known to extruder manufacturers and extrusion operators. The melting length will not be available, but it will be known whether the extruder is producing unmelted material, which could easily be introduced in the algorithm as a pass/fail classification ML. This means that the data-driven methodology presented in this paper can be used in extruder screw design by exploiting the knowledge gained from existing designs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was funded by the European Union's programme for research and innovation Horizon Europe under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action grant agreement No. 101129698-PROMATAI-Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ORCID

Nickolas D. Polychronopoulos <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3477-2979>

REFERENCES

- Bernhardt EC. *Processing of Thermoplastic Materials*. Reinhold; 1959.
- McKelvey JM. *Polymer Processing*. Wiley; 1962.
- Schenkel G. *Kunststoff-Extrudertechnik*. Hanser; 1963.
- Tadmor Z, Klein I. *Engineering Principles of Plasticating Extrusion*. Van Nostrand-Reinhold; 1970.
- Zhu F. *Extrusion Theory and Applications*. China Light Industry Press Ltd; 2001.
- Tadmor Z, Gogos GC. *Principles of Polymer Processing*. 2nd ed. Wiley; 2006.
- Chung CI. *Extrusion of Polymers: Theory and Practice*. 2nd ed. Hanser; 2011.
- Campbell GA, Spalding MA. *Analyzing and Troubleshooting Single-Screw Extruders*. Hanser; 2013. doi:10.3139/9783446432666
- Rauwendaal C. *Polymer Extrusion*. Hanser; 2013. doi:10.3139/9781569905395
- Agassant JF, Avenas P, Sergent JP, Vergnes B, Vincent M. *Mise en Forme des Polymères*. 4th ed. Lavoisier; 2014.
- Vlachopoulos J, Polychronopoulos ND. *Understanding Rheology and Technology of Polymer Extrusion*. Polydynamics, Inc.; 2019.
- Gruenschloss E. A powerful universal plasticating system for single-screw-extruders and injection-moulding machines. *Int Polym Process*. 2003;18:226-234. doi:10.3139/217.1752
- Diekhaus B, Mickley R, Stieglitz H, Dohmann H, Bornemann M. The new dimension of pipe extrusion. *Plastic Pipes Conference XVIII*. Plastic Pipes Conference Association; 2016. <https://plasticpipesconference.com/2d636d9d-ff37-4265-8cf2-ef4477689f9f>
- Tseng JW, Liu CY, Yen YK, et al. Screw extrusion-based additive manufacturing of PEEK. *Mater Des*. 2018;140:209-221. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2017.11.032
- Tian J, Zhang R, Wu Y, Xue P. Additive manufacturing of wood flour/polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) fully bio-based composites based on micro-screw extrusion system. *Mater Des*. 2021;199:109418. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2020.109418
- Mercier C, Linko P, Harper JM. *Extrusion Cooking*. American Society of Cereal Chemists; 1989.
- Händle F. *Extrusion in Ceramics*. Springer; 2007. doi:10.1007/978-3-540-27102-4
- Burbidge AS, Bridgwater J. The single screw extrusion of pastes. *Chem Eng Sci*. 1995;50:2531-2543. doi:10.1016/0009-2509(95)00107-G

19. Ghebre-Sellassie I, Ghebre-Sellassie I, Martin CE, Zhang F, DiNunzio J, Martin C. *Pharmaceutical Extrusion Technology*. CRC Press; 2003.
20. Widerøe F, Welø T. Using contrast material techniques to determine metal flow in screw extrusion of aluminium. *J Mater Process Technol*. 2013;213:1007-1018. doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2012.11.013
21. Han J, Pei J, Tong H. *Data Mining Concepts and Techniques*. 4th ed. Morgan Kaufmann; 2024. doi:10.1016/C2013-0-18660-6
22. Jordan MI, Mitchell TM. Machine learning: trends, perspectives, and prospects. *Science*. 2015;349:255-260. doi:10.1126/science.aaa8415
23. Sarker IH. Machine learning: algorithms, real-world applications and research directions. *SN Comput Sci*. 2021;2:160. doi:10.1007/s42979-021-00592-x
24. Selig M. UIUC Airfoil Coordinates Database. Version 2.0. Accessed June 13, 2024. https://m-selig.ae.illinois.edu/ads/coord_database.html
25. Wollstadt BM, Ramnath S, Shah JJ, Detwiler D, Menzel S. CarHoods10k: an industry-grade data set for representation learning and design optimization in engineering applications. *IEEE Trans Evol Comput*. 2022;26:1221-1235. doi:10.1109/TEVC.2022.3147013
26. Regenwetter L, Weaver C, Ahmed F. FRAMED: an AutoML approach for structural performance prediction of bicycle frames. *Comput Aided Des*. 2023;156:103446. doi:10.1016/j.cad.2022.103446
27. BikeCAD Bicycle Design Software. Accessed June 15, 2024. <https://www.bikecad.ca/>
28. Nextrucad. Accessed June 20, 2024. http://www.polydynamics.com/fra_programs.htm
29. Agur EE. PhD Thesis. McMaster University; 1982.
30. Agur EE, Vlachopoulos J. Numerical simulation of a single-screw plasticating extruder. *Polym Eng Sci*. 1982;22:1084-1094. doi:10.1002/pen.760221706
31. Castillo RJ. *Analysis of the Factors Affecting Barrier Screw Performance*. M.Eng. Thesis. Chemical Engineering, McMaster University, Canada; 1998.
32. Castillo RJ, Strutt D, Vlachopoulos J. Experiments and simulations with barrier screws. Paper presented at: ANTEC 2002, San Francisco, California, USA, May 5-9, 2002.
33. Darnell WH, Mol EAJ. Solids conveying in extruders. *Soc Plast Eng J*. 1956;12:20-28.
34. MacGregor A, Vlachopoulos J, Vlcek J. Computer simulation of conventional and barrier screw extruders. *J Reinf Plast Compos*. 1997;16:1270-1280. doi:10.1177/073168449701601403
35. Tadmor Z. Fundamentals of plasticating extrusion. I. A theoretical model for melting. *Polym Eng Sci*. 1966;6:185-190. doi:10.1002/pen.760060303
36. Chung CI. *Extrusion of Polymers. Theory and Practice*. Hanser; 2011.
37. Gaspar-Cunha A, Costa P, Delbem A, Monaco F, Ferreira MJ, Covas J. Evolutionary multi-objective optimization of extrusion barrier screws: data mining and decision making. *Polymers*. 2023;15(9):2212. doi:10.3390/polym15092212
38. Gaspar-Cunha A, Monaco F, Sikora J, Delbem A. Artificial intelligence in single screw polymer extrusion: learning from computational data. *Eng Appl Artif Intel*. 2022;116:105397. doi:10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105397
39. Marschik C, Roland W, Kommenda M. Extended melt-conveying models for single-screw extruders: integrating domain knowledge into symbolic regression. *Polym Eng Sci*. 2023;63:3639-3656. doi:10.1002/pen.26473
40. Herzog D, Roland W, Marschik C, Berger-Weber GR. Generalized predictions of the pumping characteristics and viscous dissipation of single-screw extruders including three-dimensional curvature effects. *Polym Eng Sci*. 2024;64(11):5566-5587. doi:10.1002/pen.26934
41. Nguyen QH, Ly HB, Ho LS, et al. Influence of data splitting on performance of machine learning models in prediction of shear strength of soil. *Math Probl Eng*. 2021;2021:1-15. doi:10.1155/2021/4832864
42. Pant A, Ramana GV. Prediction of pullout interaction coefficient of geogrids by extreme gradient boosting model. *Geotext Geomembr*. 2022;50:1188-1198. doi:10.1016/j.geotextmem.2022.08.003
43. Bessa R, Barreto GA, Coehlo DN, de Moura EP, Murta RHF. On least squares support vector regression for predicting mechanical properties of steel rebars. *Metals Basel*. 2024;14:695. doi:10.3390/met14060695
44. Hsu CW, Chang CC, Lin CJ. A practical guide to support vector classification. 2023; 1396-1400. Accessed August 5, 2024. <https://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/papers/guide/guide.pdf>
45. Cui Z, Gong G. The effect of machine learning regression algorithms and sample size on individualized behavior prediction with functional connectivity features. *Neuroimage*. 2018;178:622-637. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2018.06.001
46. Karakasidis TE, Sofos C. The electrical conductivity of ionic liquids: numerical and analytical machine learning approaches. *Fluids*. 2022;7:321. doi:10.3390/fluids7100321
47. Benos L, Tsaopoulos D, Tagarakis AC, Kateris D, Bochtis D. Optimal sensor placement and multimodal fusion for human activity recognition in agricultural tasks. *Appl Sci*. 2024;14:8520. doi:10.3390/app14188520
48. Géron A. *Hands-on Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras & TensorFlow, Concepts, Tools, and Techniques to Build Intelligent Systems*. 3rd ed. O'Reilly Media; 2022.
49. Hastie T, Tibshirani R, Friedman J. *The Elements of Statistical Learning*. 2nd ed. Springer; 2009. doi:10.1007/978-0-387-84858-7
50. Lekidis A, Georgakis A, Dalamagkas C, Papageorgiou EI. Predictive maintenance framework for fault detection in remote terminal units. *Forecasting*. 2024;6:239-265. doi:10.3390/forecast6020014
51. Akbari P, Zamani M, Mostafei A. Machine learning prediction of mechanical properties in metal additive manufacturing. *Addit Manuf*. 2024;91:104320. doi:10.1016/j.addma.2024.104320
52. Novakovic B, Kashkoush M. Modeling the matching stage of HDPE hot plate welding: a study using regression and support vector machine models. *Polym Eng Sci*. 2024;64:827-844. doi:10.1002/pen.26587
53. Awad A, Khanna R. *Efficient Learning Machines, Theories, Concepts, and Applications for Engineers and System Designers*. Apress Open; 2015. doi:10.1007/978-1-4302-5990-9
54. Sofos F, Papakonstantinou CG, Valasaki M, Karakasidis TE. Fiber-reinforced polymer confined concrete: data-driven predictions of compressive strength utilizing machine learning techniques. *Appl Sci*. 2023;13:567. doi:10.3390/app13010567

55. Ke KC, Wang JC, Nian SC. Data-driven quality prediction in injection molding: an autoencoder and machine learning approach. *Polym Eng Sci.* 2024;64:4520-4538. doi:10.1002/pen.26866
56. Huang MS, Liu CY, Ke KC. Calibration of cavity pressure simulation using autoencoder and multilayer perceptron neural networks. *Polym Eng Sci.* 2021;61:2511-2521. doi:10.1002/pen.25777
57. Nastos PT, Paliatsos AG, Koukouletsos KV, Larissi IK, Moustris KP. Artificial neural networks modeling for forecasting the maximum daily total precipitation at Athens, Greece. *Atmos Res.* 2014;144:141-150. doi:10.1016/j.atmosres.2013.11.013
58. Serwa A. Studying the effect of activation function on classification accuracy using deep artificial neural networks. *J Remote Sens GIS.* 2017;6:1000203. doi:10.4172/2469-4134.1000203
59. Tsitsis C, Alexakis DE, Moustris K, Gamvroula DE. Combining artificial neural network and driver-pressure-state-impact-response approach for evaluating a Mediterranean lake. *Water.* 2023;15(2):266. doi:10.3390/w15020266
60. Pedregosa F, Varoquaux G, Gramfort A, et al. Scikit-learn: machine learning in Python. *J Mach Learn Res.* 2011;12:2825-2830.
61. Hutter F, Kotthoff L, Vanschoren J. *Automated Machine Learning: Methods, Systems, Challenges.* Springer; 2019. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-05318-5
62. Kavzoglu T, Teke A. Advanced hyperparameter optimization for improved spatial prediction of shallow landslides using extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost). *Bull Eng Geol Environ.* 2022;81:201. doi:10.1007/s10064-022-02708-w
63. Alhakeem ZM, Jebur YM, Henedy SN, Imran H, Bernardo LFA, Hussein HM. Prediction of ecofriendly concrete compressive strength using gradient boosting regression tree combined with GridSearchCV hyperparameter-optimization techniques. *Materials.* 2022;15:7432. doi:10.3390/ma15217432
64. Ling H, Qian C, Kang W, Liang C, Chen H. Combination of support vector machine and K-fold cross validation to predict compressive strength of concrete in marine environment. *Construct Build Mater.* 2019;206:355-363. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.02.071
65. Lee S, Nguyen NH, Karamanli A, Lee J, Vo TP. Super learner machine-learning algorithms for compressive strength prediction of high performance concrete. *Struct Concr.* 2023;24:2208-2228. doi:10.1002/suco.202200424
66. Koya BP, Aneja S, Gupta R, Valeo C. Comparative analysis of different machine learning algorithms to predict mechanical properties of concrete. *Mech Adv Mater Struct.* 2022;29:4032-4043. doi:10.1080/15376494.2021.1917021
67. Moradkhani MA, Hosseini SH, Ahmadi MM. Predictive analytics for fresh concrete rheological characteristics using artificial intelligence approaches. *Mater Today.* 2024;41:110434. doi:10.1016/j.mtcomm.2024.110434
68. Ethier JG, Casukhela RK, Latimer JJ, et al. Predicting phase behavior of linear polymers in solution using machine learning. *Macromol.* 2022;55:2691-2702. doi:10.1021/acs.macromol.2c00245
69. Sathvik S, Kumar R, Ulloa N, et al. Modelling the mechanical properties of concrete produced with polycarbonate waste ash by machine learning. *Sci Rep.* 2024;14:11552. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-62412-5
70. Scikit-Learn. Accessed September 10, 2024. https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/cross_validation.html
71. Rohani A, Taki M, Abdollahpour M. A novel soft computing model (Gaussian process regression with K-fold cross validation) for daily and monthly solar radiation forecasting (part: I). *Renew Energy.* 2018;115:411-422. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2017.08.061
72. Nakatsu RT. Validation of machine learning ridge regression models using Monte Carlo, bootstrap, and variations in cross-validation. *Int J Intell Syst.* 2023;32:20220224. doi:10.1515/jisys-2022-0224
73. Liu X, Liu T, Feng P. Long-term performance prediction framework based on XGBoost decision tree for pultruded FRP composites exposed to water, humidity and alkaline solution. *Compos Struct.* 2022;284:115184. doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.115184
74. Breiman L. Random forests. *Mach Learn.* 2001;45:5-32. doi:10.1023/A:1010933404324
75. Molnar C. *Interpretable Machine Learning.* Lulu.com; 2020.
76. Chen Q, Mao P, Zhu S, Xu X, Feng H. A decision-aid system for subway microenvironment health risk intervention based on backpropagation neural network and permutation feature importance method. *Build Environ.* 2024;253:111292. doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111292
77. Peng Y, Unluer C. Analyzing the mechanical performance of fly ash-based geopolymer concrete with different machine learning techniques. *Construct Build Mater.* 2022;316:125785. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.125785
78. Nikolenko SI. *Synthetic Data for Deep Learning.* Springer; 2021. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-75178-4
79. Chen N, Zhao S, Gao Z, et al. Virtual mix design: prediction of compressive strength of concrete with industrial wastes using deep data augmentation. *Constr Build Mater.* 2022;323:126580. doi:10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.126580

How to cite this article: Polychronopoulos ND, Moustris K, Karakasidis T, et al. Machine learning for screw design in single-screw extrusion. *Polym Eng Sci.* 2025;1-17. doi:10.1002/pen.27170